

High Performance Work Practices, Entrepreneurial Orientation and Organisation Excellence in Nigerian HEIs: A Correlational Analysis*

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**Funding for the research from which this article is derived is provided by the Tertiary Education Trust Fund of Nigeria through TETFund Institution-Based Research Grant (Batch 5 RP Disbursement) to the Federal Polytechnic, Offa, Nigeria*

ABSTRACT: Necessity for excellent performance in organisations (organisational excellence - OE) have taken pre-eminence for a long time, Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) inclusive. Towards ensuring excellent performances, High Performance Work Practices (HPWPs) have been found to be necessary complements to the excellent performances. It is also on record that this aim is only possible through an enabling environment that can be provided by a disposition towards entrepreneurship (entrepreneurial orientation - EO). The study uses the Ability, Motivation and Opportunity (AMO) framework to establish a theoretical framework for the research. Data was collected from members of academic staff in selected public HEIs in the North-Central and South-Western geo-political zones of Nigeria. The study employed multistage sampling procedure with the use of survey questionnaires. The sample used was 420 questionnaires distributed and analyzed through SPSS 20.0. The correlation results show strong relationship between HPWPs and OE as well as EO and OE. The study recommends sustainability of HPWPs and EO in Nigerian HEIs towards World Class operation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Jarratt Report of 1995 in the United Kingdom shifted World attention to the concept of corporatization of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). The concept posits that universities should imbibe an industrial model or “ethos” by means of transferring business principles into the HEIs’

However, the prime place of a bundle of human capital management practices in the move towards excellent performances in organisations (HEIs inclusive) has long been identified. It is seen as a strategic move to ensuring quality performances in organisations (Fu, 2013). These bundles of human capital practices are referred to as High Performance Work Practices (HPWPs) which go a long way in affecting performance (Fabi, Lacoursiere & Raymond, 2015, Karatepe, 2013, Ogbonnaya, Daniels & Connolly, 2016).

To be able to exploit the benefits derivable from HPWP system, organisation participants, especially leaders, must display entrepreneurial orientation if the aims, objectives and orientation of the institution would be achieved optimally (Affendy, Asmat-Nizam, Abdul-Talib, Abdul Rahim, 2011). This has spurred interest in entrepreneurial orientation in organisation. This is confirmed by the study conducted on the link between entrepreneurial orientation and performance (Lumpkin & Dess, 1996); its effect on effective and efficient management of education institutions (Frank, Kokura, Lueger & Mugler, 2005). Yokoyama’s (2006) work dealt with interactive effect of entrepreneurship, management, governance and leadership in Japanese and UK universities. These researches showed how entrepreneurial orientation had affected organisational excellence differently.

To this end, this paper intends to explore the correlational interaction between high performance work practices and organisational excellence in one hand as well as the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and organisational excellence on the other hand. These are the bases that spur the interest in this paper.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT/JUSTIFICATION

There are many challenges facing HEIs in Nigeria with respect to HPWPs as they impact on organizational excellence. This is more compounded due to lack of entrepreneurial orientation towards exploiting opportunities to improve upon the areas of deficiencies.

In Nigeria, the staffing situation at the HEIs level is highly undesirable. The paucity of high quality of academic staff is further compounded by the rapid rate of establishment of universities, especially private universities and those established for political expediency, in the country in the past few years. The total staff strength of 34,712 translates to a students/academic staff ratio of 40:1 which is very high. The ratio for private and federal universities is fair while that of the state universities is very high. Nigerian HEIs have not been able to attract, select and retain good staff (Bamiro, 2012).

Other major issues are improper staff recruitment which Bamiro (2012) refers to as 'endogamy' in staff hiring - the growing in-breeding in staffing and limited ability to attract foreign staff especially in the core disciplines of science, mathematics and basic technology, special education, computer science, technology, law, engineering, medicine and surgery. This leads to localization of human resources in Nigerian HEIs (Oyedeki, 2016). Inadequate staff development programme for training and re-training of staff also affects the vibrancy of staff in Nigerian HEIs (Asiyai, 2013).

Furthermore, proprietors and leaders in Nigerian public HEIs are not dynamic in attracting funds, researches, students etc all of which had contributed to below-excellence performance level (Nigerian Tribune, March 2010). The leaders are not expected to be entrepreneurially-oriented so as to be prepared to provide the kind of education required in this modern competitive World. Despite the fact that the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) granted academic, financial and institutional autonomy to federal universities through government policy release in May, 2000 and University Miscellaneous Act of 2003, there is gross underutilisation of the financial autonomy segment of the provisions of the policy release and the Act. The former Executive Secretary, National Universities Commission in Nigeria lament that most universities are failing in the exercise of this right- financial autonomy (Okojie, 2011). As at October, 2013, over One Hundred Billion Naira (\$500m) was idle as unaccessed funding by Nigerian higher education institutions domiciled with the TETF and (Daily Trust, Oct. 10, 2013). Unfortunately, this funding allocated may not be optimally accessed by the HEIs as the latter did not adequately access the earlier funding allocations.

Olabisi (2012) observed that there would continue to be an increase in the number of Nigerians seeking higher education admission internationally as Gabriel (2011) analysed the penchant of Nigerian parents for foreign education for their children. Nigerian HEIs are unable to seize the opportunity in the education market to provide for more Nigerians in need of higher education. An entrepreneurially-oriented leader will exploit this opportunity.

Tabiu (2019) found a direct and indirect effects of high performance work practices on organizational performance in public universities in Nigeria. Muduli and McLean (2020) found out the capability of high performance work system in predicting organizational performance. Ahmad, Raziq, Rheman and Allan (2019) however found out that different dimensions of HPWPs and varying relationship and effects on organisational performance outcomes. Dayarathna, Dowling and Bartram (2019) found positive outcomes of high performance work practices on organizational effectiveness, to bring about a positive attitudinal climate among employees. All these researches are not conducted in HEIs and are not all fully providing the same result.

Cho and Lee (2018) investigated and found out that only innovativeness influences performance but other subdimensions of entrepreneurial orientation do not. On the other hand, Hassan and Mohammed (2020) and Bello-Pintado, Kaufmann and de Cerio (2018) found a positive and significant effect of entrepreneurial orientation on performance with consideration of ambidextrous on the relationship by Nofiani, Indarti, Lukito-Budi and Manik (2020). The results are not fully complementary.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The main research question is to find out is there relationship between High Performance Work Practices (HPWP) and Organisational Excellence on one hand and entrepreneurial orientation and Organisational Excellence in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Nigeria?

The specific research questions are

- (a) Is there any relationship between High Performance Work Practices (HPWP) and Organisational excellence?
- (b) Is there any relationship between Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) and Organisational Excellence (OE)?

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The main objective of this paper is to investigate the relationship between High Performance Work Practices (HPWP) and Organisational Excellence on one hand and entrepreneurial orientation and Organisational Excellence in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Nigeria.

The specific objectives are

- (a) To determine the relationship between High Performance Work Practices (HPWP) and Organisational excellence
- (b) To examine the relationship between Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) and Organisational Excellence (OE).

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The main hypothesis of this paper is determining the relationship between High Performance Work Practices (HPWP) and Organisational Excellence on one hand and entrepreneurial orientation and Organisational Excellence in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Nigeria.

The specific hypotheses are:

- (a) There is no relationship between High Performance Work Practices (HPWP) and Organisational excellence
- (b) There is no relationship between Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) and Organisational Excellence (OE).

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

ORGANISATIONAL EXCELLENCE

The requirements for quality performances by organisations has been widened to embrace business excellence interchangeably referred to as organizational excellence (Kanji, 2002; Tata Ratan, 2007; Klefsjö, Bergquist & Garvare, 2008). Organisational excellence will be used in this paper because this research is based on service industry- academic institutions.

With the seminal book titled *In Search of Excellence* by Peters and Waterman (1982), greater attention, practice and research had been focused on excellence in organisations. They viewed organisational excellence as depicted in an organisation that was "...adroit at continually responding to change of any sort in their environment". It refers to an organisation's ability to "...track, revamp, adjust, transform, and adapt" to shifts in customers' needs, improvement in the skills of their competitors, perturbation in the mood of the public, realignment of the forces in the international trade as well as shifts in government regulations. Organisational excellence involved exertion of extra-ordinary energy above and beyond the call of duty.

European Foundation for Quality Management (EFQM, 2019) which aims at organisational excellence observes that it revolves around "the primacy of the customer; the need to take a long term stakeholder centric view and understanding the cause and effect linkages between why an organisation does something, how it does it and what it achieves as a consequence of its actions".

To Dawei, Alan and Simon (2011) it connotes the combination of the excellence of the internal operations of an organisation and excellence in those external performances that are measurable.

Thus, organisational excellence comprises efficient satisfaction of all stakeholders to an organisation in a sustainable way.

The cores of organisational excellence that could be used to measure and/or energise an organisation for excellence performance, as posited by Peters and Waterman's (1982) *In Search Of Excellence* are eight back to basics of management excellence. These are: a bias for action; close to the customer; autonomy and entrepreneurship. Others are: productivity through people; hands-on, value-driven; stick to the knitting; simple form, lean staff and; simultaneous loose-tight properties.

HIGH PERFORMANCE WORK PRACTICES (HPWPs)

The emergence of the strategic human resource management field has been associated with a shift in scholarly interest from control-based personnel management to more commitment-based HRM practices termed high performance. In the study of human resources management, there are various terms used to refer to such practices. It is sometimes referred to as High Performance Work Systems (Appelbaum *et al.*, 2000), high commitment human resources practices (Whitener, 2001) as well as high involvement work practices (Guthrie, 2001). The term used by Appelbaum *et al.*, (2000) HPWS shall be adapted with a change of system with practices.

It has been suggested by scholars that as a way of understanding the concept of HPWP, human resources practices must be studied from three perspectives. These are the universalistic, contingency and configurational perspective. Furthermore, researchers have conceptualized HPWP through various means. Some scholars view HPWP as a collection of multiple and discrete practices with no explicit linkages (Guest and Hoque, 1994; Boselie et al. (2005) while others (e.g. Delery and Shaw, 2001) suggest that single superior practices are inadequate to produce higher performance if they are viewed as without interdependence on other practices. Rather, HR practices complement each other to support sustainable success.

The cores or dimensions of High Performance Work Practices (HPWPs) could be derived from the three components of AMO (Ability, Motivation and Opportunity) for ability-enhancing practices, motivation-enhancing practices and opportunity-enhancing practices. These are in the areas of improving the knowledge, skills and abilities (KSA) of employees; investment in human resources practices with the aim of motivating employee behaviors and; satisfying employees' wish to be involved in decision-making and organisational outcomes especially when they reach certain levels in the organisation. (Jiang et al., 2012).

Research has found out direct and indirect effects of high performance work practices on organizational performance in public universities in Nigeria (Tabiu, 2019). Ahmad, Raziq, Rheman and Allan (2019) found that different dimensions of HPWPs had varying relationship and effects on organisational performance outcomes which is in agreement with the finding of Dayarathna, Dowling and Bartram (2019) on organisational effectiveness. Muduli and McLean (2020) concluded that there is a capability of high performance work system in predicting organizational performance.

ENTREPRENEURIAL ORIENTATION

Researches geared towards explaining how entrepreneurs constantly behave instead of what they do - a shift from the content theory to the process theory of entrepreneurship, led to studies in entrepreneurial orientation (Lumpkin & Dess, 1996). It is simply a process that is concerned with the practices, methods and decision-making styles that managers used as a strategic choice alternative in a dynamic generative process (Richard, Barnett, Dwyer & Chadwick, 2004). In their seminal paper on entrepreneurial orientation, Lumpkin and Dess (1996) viewed it as the totality of not only processes and practices but also decisions that led to new entry. It is the predisposition of an individual, group and/or organisation towards being innovative in risk-taking activities and aggressively pursuing it with the aim of exploiting a discovered opportunity.

The cores or dimensions of entrepreneurial orientation are: autonomy; innovativeness; risk-taking; proactiveness, and competitive aggressiveness based on concept extension of Lumpkin & Dess, (1996) by Covin and Slevin (1989), the entrepreneurial orientation dimensions had been expanded to five. Many studies had been conducted on entrepreneurial orientation as a construct and the first-order and second-order items but they nevertheless provided a basis for our understanding and measurement of entrepreneurial orientation in individuals and organisations. Studies had been conducted to present these dimensions in formative and reflective manners (George & Marino, 2011).

While Cho and Lee (2018) found out that only innovativeness influences performance but other subdimensions of entrepreneurial orientation do not, Hassan and Mohammed (2020) and Bello-Pintado, Kaufmann and de Cerio (2018) found a positive and significant effect of entrepreneurial orientation on performance. Nofiani, Indarti, Lukito-Budi and Manik (2020) also agree with that entrepreneurship orientation has relationship with organisational performance.

IV. RESEARCH METHOD

Primary data of quantitative research design through survey instrument of questionnaire will be used. The total population of the academic staff in Nigerian public higher education institutions is 66,392 out of which a sample of 420 will be selected through multistage sampling method. The sample to be taken will be one university, one polytechnic and one college of education each from each of the geo-political zone. A minimum of two institutions will be selected from each of the geo-political zone and from a state. Six institutions will be selected in all.

Wave analysis, Exploratory factor analysis and correlational analysis will be conducted using the principal component method. SPSS version 20 will be used because it has adequate provisions for bootstrapping to improve probabilistic measurement and; missing value analysis to determine the extent and pattern of missing values et cetera. The data will be analysed by following the specific procedures stipulated by Pallant (2013) for relevant analyses to answering research questions and testing for the two hypotheses. The variables will be operationalized as below:

Table 1

Operationalisation of Measurement of Variables

VARIABLE	OPERATIONAL DEFINITION	NO OF ITEMS	SOURCE OF ADAPTATION
Organisational Excellence	Peters & Waterman (1982)	Items 1 - 21	Bou-Llusar, Escrig-Tena, Roca-Puig & Beltran-Martin (2008)
High Performance Work Practices	Murphy and Olsen, (2009); Obeidat, Mitchell and Bray, (2016)	Ability-enhancing, motivation-enhancing and Opportunity-enhancing	Murphy and Olsen, (2009); Obeidat, Mitchell and Bray, (2016) on Ability-enhancing, motivation-enhancing and Opportunity-enhancing
Entrepreneurial Orientation	Lumpkin & Dess (1996)	Items 1 - 3 (Autonomy); Items 4 - 6 (Innovation); Items 7 - 10 (Risk-Taking); Items 11 - 13 (Competitive Aggressiveness); Items 14 - 16 (Proactiveness)	Alexandrova (2004) - Autonomy; Miller and Friesen (1982) - Innovation; Miller and Friesen (1983) - Risk-Taking; Lumpkin and Dess (2001) - Competitive Aggressiveness; Morris and Paul (1987) - Proactiveness

RESULTS

Out of the four hundred and twenty questionnaires distributed, three hundred and forty-three were returned. Out of the returned questionnaires, thirty cases were removed as unusable because they had up to 15% missing data based on the rule of thumb as suggested by Hair, Black, Babin and Anderson (2010). The usable cases were three hundred and thirteen which were used for the purpose of data analysis which is very good as the consensus in survey research on response rate is that a response rate of 50% is considered adequate, 60% is good enough and 70% is very good for analysis (Babbie and Mouton, 2001). The non-response bias analysis through wave analysis and eta square shows that there is no significantly significant difference between the early and late responders and the effect size through eta square is small and negligible. The data was cleaned for error, missing data, outliers and requirements for correlational analysis like normality, linearity, homoscedasticity and **multicollinearity all of which were in perfect order.**

The profile of the respondents shows that 79.2% of the respondents fall within the age group of 30yrs < 60yrs with 71.6% being male and 28.1% being female and .3% missing. University workers constitute 27.80% of the respondents while 42.81% and 29.39% were polytechnic and colleges of education workers. The length of service of respondents falls majorly within 5yrs < 30yrs with 87.7%; their education level from masters and above is 71.8% while majority of respondents are below senior lecturer in both the university, polytechnic and colleges of education with 59.2%.

A factor analysis was conducted that showed that organisational excellence variable had twenty-one items while four items were deleted after one factor extraction leaving twenty items for further analysis. The four items deleted are numbers 4, 15, 17 and 18 due to small factor loading as in Table 2 below

Table 2
Factor Analysis for Organisational Excellence

Items	Factor Loading
Staff have high commitment to my institution	.778
My institution has become more efficient in the discharge of its responsibility to students	.713
Through deliberate and conscious effort of my institution, knowledge of efficient operation management has improved among staff in my institution	.690
Staff are willing to work extra time with a view to achieving the goals of my institution	.683
Staffs in my institution always show high level of initiative	.672
Staffs are willing to identify and provide solution to work problems in my institution	.652
Staff share the values of my institution	.647
My institution has become more efficient in the discharge of its responsibility to staff	.619
Staff opinions are being used to improve work performance in my institution	.618
My institution has contributed to socio-economic development of the immediate society.	.607
Services provided to students are better in my institution than other similar institutions	.583
The services provided by my institution has improved students' satisfaction	.568
Staff training and development has improved in my institution	.566
Even, if given opportunity of other jobs, staffs are willing to remain in my institution	.551
Communication with students in my institution has improved over time (e.g. SMS, students' e-mail services, robust and interactive institution portal et cetera)	.520
The society in which my institution is located has benefited from modernity through the activities of my institution	.518
My institution has provided more opportunity for people in the immediate environment to get advantage of higher institution training	.504
The activities of my institution have reduced the crime rate in the environment	.493
Companies, institutions et cetera are now willing to give consultancy jobs to my institution	.492
My institution has been able to attract more students interested in seeking for offer of admission	.462
My institution has been able to drastically improve its revenue base apart from the subvention from government	.341
Eigen Value	7.378
Total Variance Explained (%)	53.921
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.911
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity approx Chi-square	2381.540
Df	210
Sig.	0.000

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. A 1 component extracted

Factor Analysis on High Performance Work Practices showed that the variable had twenty-three (23) items while four items (2,9, 13 and 22) were deleted due to small factor loading. This is in Table 3 below

Table 3
Factor Analysis for High Performance Work Practices

Item	Factor Loading
My institution is disposed to selecting skillful employees	.744
There is good quality of work life in my institution	.722
Teams are encouraged to be self-managing	.712
My institution plays important role on staffing processes in this institution	.702
My institution does formal job analysis before recruiting	.700
There is effective communication in my institution	.693
My institution is highly selective in recruiting	.685
There is provision of incentive pay based on performance appraisal	.671
My institution places importance on training and skill development	.661
My institution values imparting skills in employee	.660
Employees are allowed to participation in decision-making	.650
My institution ensures conduct of performance appraisal	.626
Diversity is encouraged in my institution	.626
Information is well shared in my institution	.624
Employees are given sense of ownership in my institution	.605
Employees are involved in job design in my institution	.577
Work assignments are flexible in my institution	.549
Employees are given choice in the performance of their responsibilities	.545
Status distinctions and barriers are reduced in my institution	.515
My institution pays higher wages compared to its counterparts around	.481
A greater portion of staff in my institution have enjoyed at least a training and development programme	.480
My institution encourages promotion from within	.472
Employment security is guaranteed in my institution	.414
Eigen Value	8.851
Total Variance Explained (%)	56.348
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.929
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity approx Chi-square	3131.865
Df	253
Sig.	0.000

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. A 1 component extracted

The last Factor Analysis on Entrepreneurial Orientation showed that entrepreneurial orientation variable had sixteen items while two items (3 and 15) were deleted after one factor extraction due to small loading thereby leaving fourteen items for further analysis as below

Table 4

Factor Analysis for Entrepreneurial Orientation

Items	Factor Loading
My institution adopts a very competitive (i.e. undo other similar institutions) posture in its policies and activities	.730
My institution is always in active search for big opportunities	.678
My institution always responds to actions initiated by other institutions especially in the provision of educational services	.674
There have been new educational services introduced in my institution in the past four years compared to similar other institutions in the immediate environment	.673
When confronted with decision-making situations involving uncertainty, my institution usually adopts a cautious "wait and see" posture in order to minimize the probability of making costly decisions	.673
There exists a very strong emphasis on and acceleration in research and development, intellectual leadership, and innovation in my institution	.652
There is a high level of delegation of authority to the departments, faculties and task units in my institution	.649
New educational services introduced by my institution have always been dramatic (e.g. changes from analogue to digital operations)	.646
Staffs are encouraged in my institution to seize and explore "chancy" opportunities	.642
There is a culture of strong proclivity to high risk projects (with chances of very high returns) in my institution	.634
Bold and wide-ranging acts are viewed as useful and are a common practice in my institution	.634
Cautious and pragmatic approach is used by my institution to adjust to any problem	.633
My institution allows and encourages staff to develop the will to be self-directed in the pursuit of opportunities	.581
My institution always wants to avoid clashes with other similar institution in the areas of new educational services, administrative techniques as well as operating technologies	.537
New venture innovators are shielded from the institutional and resource constraints in my institution	.424
Decision-making in my institution is always an outcome of compromise of conflicting demands	.419
Eigen Value	6.211
Total Variance Explained (%)	53.658
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.909
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity approx Chi-square	1745.575
Df	120
Sig.	0.000

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. A 1 component extracted

A reliability test was conducted which gave the results as summarised below

Table 5
Reliability Analyses

Factor	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Organisational Excellence	17	0.901
High Performance Work Practices	19	0.923
Entrepreneurial Orientation	14	0.894

Table 5 above summarised the reliability examination of the scales after taking into consideration of the dropped items. As shown, the Cronbach's alphas values for all factors ranged from .894 to .923. These results showed that all factors of organisational excellence, high performance work practices and entrepreneurial orientation had acceptable internal consistency.

V. CORRELATION TEST

To explore the relationship between set(s) of dependent and independent variables so as to examine the strength and direction of the linear relationship between them, a correlation analysis is carried out (Hair *et al.*, 2010; Pallant, 2013, Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014). The strength of the relationship between two variables is determined by the magnitude of the absolute value of the coefficient (i.e. the -/+ sign needed to be ignored). Based on the recommended guideline to interpreting the strength of the relationship between two variables (r) by Cohen (1988) as presented by Pallant (2013), a r = ± .10 to .29 is small, r = ± .30 to .49 is medium while r = ± .50 to 1.0 is large.

The summary of the Pearson correlation between the independent variables and dependent variable under study was depicted in the Table 6 below

Table 6
Pearson Correlations for Independent Variable and Dependent Variable

VARIABLE	Organisational Excellence	High Performance Work Practices	Entrepreneurial Orientation
Organisational Excellence	1		
High Performance Work Practices	.755**	1	
Entrepreneurial Orientation	.641**	.790**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 6 above shows the relationship among all three variables in the study. The correlation coefficients (r) indicate the strength of the relationship between the variables and the correlation coefficient for all latent variables. All the correlations are found under the threshold of .90 thereby eliminating high multicollinearity (Hair *et al.*, 2010). On the overall, the correlation values of the variables showed correlation coefficients values of above .5 which ranged from .641 to .790.

These results indicate high correlation between variables. Specifically, the relationship between organisational excellence and high performance work practices is r = .755; between organisational excellence and entrepreneurial orientation is r = .641. Furthermore, the relationship between high performance work practices and entrepreneurial orientation is r = .790. The r values which ranged from .641 to .790 which was above .5, showing highly strong relationship among the variables. Since the coefficients in Table 6 showed higher than .5, it meant that the variables largely influenced each other.

To get an idea of how much variance two variables shared, there is needs to calculate the coefficient of determination. This is done by squaring the r and multiplying by 100. The r² is shown in the Table 7 below as derived from Table 6 above

Table 7
Variable to Get the Coefficient of Determination

Squared Correlation of the

VARIABLE	Organisational Excellence	High Performance Work Practices	Entrepreneurial Orientation
Organisational Excellence	1		
High Performance Work Practices	.5700	1	
Entrepreneurial Orientation	.4109	.6241	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From the Table 7 above, organisational excellence and high performance work practices shared 57% of their variance; organisational excellence and entrepreneurial orientation shared above 41% of their variance. Furthermore, high performance work practices and entrepreneurial orientation shared over 62% of their variance. This is quite a respectable amount of variance explained.

VI. DISCUSSIONS

The analysis carried out have helped in answering the two research questions and assisted in the test of the two hypotheses stated.

The first research question reads as Is there any relationship between High Performance Work Practices (HPWP) and Organisational excellence? This question was answered from the output of the correlation analysis depicted in Table 6 above. This showed that a change in the high-performance work practices variable leads to a significant positive change in the level of organisational excellence that was achieved. This is in agreement with previous findings (Ahmad, *et al.*, 2020; Muhammad and Abdullah, 2016; Karatepe and Olugbade, 2016).

The second research question reads as Is there any relationship between Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) and Organisational Excellence (OE)? This question is answered from the output of the correlation analysis depicted in the Table 6 above. This showed that if there is a change in the entrepreneurial orientation variable, it led to a significant positive change in the level of organisational excellence that was achieved. This is the outcome of previous researches by Lumpkin and Dess (1996); Yokoyama (2006); Bello-Pintado *et al.* (2018) and; Nofiani, *et al.* (2020)

The outcomes of the test of hypotheses, the significance and the findings are as presented in the Table 8 below

Table 8
Summary of the Hypotheses Tested by Using Correlation

HYPOTHESIS	SIGNIFICANT	FINDING
H1	Yes	Supported
H2	Yes	Supported

VII. CONCLUSION

From the analyses carried out, it can be factually concluded that there are strong linear relationship between high performance work practices and organisational excellence on one hand and entrepreneurial orientation and organisational excellence on the other hand. The correlational results proved that.

VIII. MANAGERIAL IMPLICATION

The implications of the findings for management actions are that management of Nigerian HEIs should put in place activities that will enhance employees’ ability; motivate them and provide them with almost limitless opportunities. Furthermore, employees should be involved in decision-making and organisational outcomes especially when they reach certain levels in the organization.

Apart from that, managers of Nigerian HEIs to promote autonomy; innovativeness; risk-taking; proactiveness, and competitive aggressiveness among the academic staffs of their institutions. These will engender excellent performances towards making their institutions more visible in the World academic landscape.

IX. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This study only covers the South-West and North-Central geo-political zones of Nigeria. Further researches are needed to cover other zones viz: North-East; North-West; South-East and South-South geopolitical zones of Nigeria.

Academic staff only are covered but they are not the only cadre of staff that can influence excellent operations in Nigerian HEIs. Junior and senior non-academic staff as well as technologists in universities can be investigated.

The study assumes that it is only high performance work practices and entrepreneurial orientation that have relationship with excellent performances. Factors like the environment, globalization et cetera also have relationship which must be further investigated.

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